

COMPUTER NETWORKS AND NETWORK TECHNOLOGY PROGRAMS IN ACADEMICS: A STUDY OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract:

Information Technology is an important name for the development and modernization. This is most important and valuable for the purpose of internetworking and communication development among the stakeholders. Network Technology is actually an important part of IT and Computing. Initially only Computer Science treated as a field of study and gradually other streams also have been arrived into academics viz. Computer Engineering, Computing, Computational Science, Information Technology, Informatics, Information Science, Information Systems. The rising growth of IT and Computing fields and its sub fields brought us various others viz. Web Technology, Network Technology, Multimedia Technology, Database Technology and traditional core area Software Technology. Hence Network Technology is become an important field of Computing and IT. Various universities internationally have started educational program in the field with Bachelors, Masters and even Doctoral Programs. In India also recent past large number of universities have been emerged and developed and many of these have started program in this field. This paper is a kind of study on private universities highlighting the emerging program in the field and its future potentialities in Indian context.

Keywords: Information Technology, Computing, Network Technology, Academics, Indian Universities, Research and Development

Introduction

The Networking field is growing and improving rapidly in recent past, organizations and institutions are using Networking Technologies and allied systems. And as a result universities and other educational institutions are offering academic programs in the fields leading to Diploma, Bachelors, Masters programs [1], [7]. It is worthy to note that the Masters program available in different track viz. Science, Technology, Management. The networking technology is these days accustom with wireless systems, Bluetooth, converged networks, Internet of Things (IoT), Cloud Computing, Virtualization etc [2], [3]. The areas are still continuing and depending upon organizations and institutions. It is worthy to note that Indian academic bodies specially the private universities are playing well in respect of offering new age and skill based networking related programs viz.

- Computer Networks
- Network Technology
- Cloud Computing
- Virtualization
- Information Security/ Cyber Security/ Information Assurance etc.

It is important to note that, this trend is growing and improving where universities are offering these areas as a specialization/ concentration/ major etc. This study shows how Indian universities have started program in this field and their versatility [4].

Objective and Agenda

The current paper is conceptual and theoretical in nature and thus it is mainly deals with following aim and objectives—

- To learn basics about the mother subjects of the Computer Networks/ Network Technology in brief and easy manner.
- To know about the programs in this field with their current nomenclatures, way of delivery etc.
- To learn about the basics of Higher Educational Systems in India especially private universities in India.
- To learn about the skill based educational programs and allied areas in the fields of Networking and Communication Technology.
- To learn about the MSc and MTech programs in this fields available in the private universities in India.

Methods

The current paper is conceptual in nature and thus deals with theoretical methods of research. It is mainly a joint work and study concentrated on Networking Technology education in India with special reference to private universities. It is worthy to note that the study is concentrated on private universities in India and thus for studying current status several websites have been used as a source of knowledge namely, UGC, AICTE. To reach the latest on private universities website of UGC considered as main tool.

Computing and Information Sciences: The Backbone of Networking Technologies

Network Technology is an important component of the domain Information Technology and allied branches. The field is available with different nomenclatures with little different features and characteristics [5], [6]. Important to note that, the field Computing and Information Technology now gained and treated as a big science and technology. Internationally in Computing among the areas few popular and emerging are include—

- **Computer Science:** Computer Science is theoretical and mathematical in nature and dealing internal and core of computers; mainly hardware systems. Designing, development of computer systems is the core and main aspects of Computer Science. It is also focused on different kind of software and programming languages.
- **Computer Engineering:** Computer Engineering is a discipline and field responsible for the core of hardware and mainly designing, manufacturing and development of computer systems. Software and programming languages is the partial focused area of Computer Engineering [9], [10].
- **Computer Systems:** In Computer Systems the core topic or agenda is software systems and computer in diverse fields. It is also called as ‘*Computing*’ in some countries and in India also this is available as ‘*Computer Applications*’.
- **Merged Computing Fields:** There are many subjects have been developed in Computing track with merged concepts of two related fields viz. Computer Science and Engineering, Computer Science and Application etc.

In another approach, Information track is fully concentrated on collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination of information with different kind of tools and technologies viz.

- **Information Technology:** Among the components of Information Technology the core are includes Network Technologies, Database Technologies, Web Technologies, Communication Technologies and Multimedia Technologies and Traditional software Technologies.
- **Information and Communication Technology:** It is similar to IT but core focus with Communication and Network Technologies. It is widely available useful and important in different sectors.
- **Informatics:** The field is similar to the Information Science but here due concentration has been provided to the Information Technologies and Management. It has also take care of fundamentals of Information and similar contents.
- **Information Science:** This is concentrated on the collection, selection, organization; processing, management and dissemination of information and for this several IT components are used. Importantly here additional focus and concentration are provided to the social sciences and management issues.
- **Merged Information related domains:** Apart from the above fields internationally many other fields have been developed and among these important are ‘Information System and Technology’, ‘Information Science and Technology’, ‘Computer and Information Science’ etc [8], [11].

Indian Higher Education & Private Universities

India is a large and one of biggest nation in the world and having different kind of Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) including universities, colleges, polytechnics etc. Importantly in recent past a large number of private universities have been established nationwide and in almost all the states. It is worthy to note that most of these private universities have started new age programs and advanced interdisciplinary programs and in computing also there are lots of programs. The Table: 1 is depicted the list of private universities (state wise) herewith—

Table: 1- Depicted Private Universities in India

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7
2	Assam	5

3	Bihar	2
4	Chhattisgarh	9
5	Gujarat	30
6	Haryana	20
7	Himachal Pradesh	17
8	Jharkhand	7
9	Karnataka	14
10	Meghalaya	8
11	Mizoram	1
12	Madhya Pradesh	24
13	Maharashtra	9
14	Manipur	1
15	Nagaland	3
16	Odisha	4
17	Punjab	15
18	Rajasthan	46
19	Sikkim	5
20	Tripura	1
21	Uttar Pradesh	29
22	Uttarakhand	13
23	West Bengal	9
Grand Total		279

The highest number of private universities have been established in the state of Rajasthan (46) and then second Gujarat (30). Importantly in these private universities several emerging and skill specific degrees are offered. Though nationally other HEIs are also important and apart from private universities their data are provided in Table: 2 herewith.

Table: 2-Universities in India: A Snapshot

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Institutes of National Importance (INI)	92	Pan India with 28 States and UT
Central Universities	47	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	370	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	290	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	123	Except some states and UT

Table: 3-Private Universities in India including emerging specializations/ Major in MSc Program in IT & Computing Field.

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities	No. of Universities with Specialized Programs	No. of with Focused MSc in Computing/IT related area
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7	1	5
2	Assam	5	Nil	Nil
3	Bihar	2	Nil	Nil
4	Chhattisgarh	9	1	1
5	Gujarat	30	6	15
6	Haryana	20	1	1
7	Himachal Pradesh	17	Nil	Nil
8	Jharkhand	7	Nil	Nil
9	Karnataka	14	1	4
10	Meghalaya	8	Nil	Nil
11	Mizoram	1	Nil	Nil

12	Madhya Pradesh	24	Nil	Nil
13	Maharashtra	9	Nil	Nil
14	Manipur	1	Nil	Nil
15	Nagaland	3	Nil	Nil
16	Odisha	4	Nil	Nil
17	Punjab	15	3	3
18	Rajasthan	46	1	1
19	Sikkim	5	Nil	Nil
20	Tripura	1	Nil	Nil
21	Uttar Pradesh	29	4	5
22	Uttrakhand	13	Nil	Nil
23	West Bengal	9	1	2
Grand Total		279	19	37

According to this study it has been noted that as a whole India has total 279 number of private or self finance universities and among these 19 are offered program on specialized areas. Importantly 37 programs are offered in the areas of Networking and emerging technologies with the nomenclature/ tag 'MSc'. It is noted that Gujarat has total 15 specialized programs with first rank and then second rank by the Uttar Pradesh and Arunachal Pradesh with total 5 number of programs.

It is noted that many universities have different nomenclatures in the field of Network Technologies such as—

- MSc-Tele Communication
- MSc- Networking
- MSc-Call Centre Communication
- MSc-Digital Forensic & Information Security
- MSc-Network Technology and Management etc

It is important to note that many universities have started program on Network Technologies with Engineering degrees at Masters level with ME and MTech degree. The universities are mainly offered programs with concentration or specialization among the related nomenclature few important are include—

- Network Security
- Mobile Technology

- Cloud Computing
- Internet Engineering
- Telecommunication with Networking etc.

The table: 4 has depicted in detail in this regard with the name of the universities and specialization offered.

Table: 4- Depicted Cloud Computing specialization in Masters Engineering track

Sl. No.	Private Universities in India offering Cloud and Allied Technologies Programs (Engineering Track/Masters)	
	Universities	Programs
1	Nirma University	MTech-IT (Networking- with Minor IoT & Cloud) MTech-CE (Information & Network Security with Minor IoT & Cloud)
2	Ansal University	MTech-CSE (Network & Information Security) MTech-CSE (Tele-commutation & Mobile Technology)
3	The Northcap University	MTech-CSE (Networking)
4	Dayanand Sagar University	MTech- CSE (Cloud Computing)
5	JSS Science & Technology University	MTech- Network & Internet Engineering
6	PES University	MTech-CSE (Cloud Computing)
7	Reva University	MTech- Data Engineering & Cloud Computing MTech-Computer Network Engineering
8	Sandip University	MTech-Cloud Technology & Information Security
9	Chandigarh University	ME (Hons) CSE (Cloud Computing)-IBM
10	Guru Kashi University	MTech- Cloud Computing (MSc eligible)
11	J.E.C.R.C University	MTech- CSE (Computer Network & Security)

12	Manipal University	MTech- / Information & Network Security- with CDAC
13	Amity University	MTech- Computer Network & Information Security
14	Sharda University	MTech-CSE (Networking)

Among these universities highest number of programs are offered by the following universities, viz.

- Nirma University,
- Ansal University
- Reva University

They have total 2 programs related with the Networking and Communication Technologies. The list of universities having MSc program in the private universities are noted as under (refer Table1: 5)—

Table: 5-Private Universities in India offering Networking and Allied specializations/ Major in MSc Program

Specialized Masters Programs in IT & Computing Field		
	Universities	Programs
1	Himalayan University, Arunachal Pradesh	MSc-Tele Communication MSc- Networking MSc-Call Centre Communication
2	Ganpat University, Gujarat	MSc (Tech)- IT Infrastructure Management Services MSc (Tech)- Mobile Application MSc-IT (Cyber Security)
3	G.L.S. University, Gujarat	MSc-IT- Mobile Computing MSc-IT- Network & System Administration
4	Navrachana University, Gujarat	MSc-IT (Network Administration)
5	R.K. University, Gujarat	MSc-IT (Cloud Technology) MSc-IT (Infrastructure Managed Service)
6	Amity University, Haryana	MSc-Network Technology & Management)

7	Institute of Trans-Disciplinary Health Sciences and Technology University, Karnataka	MSc-CS (Cyber Security)
8	Mody University of Science and Technology, Rajasthan	MSc-Digital Forensic & Information Security
9	Amity University, UP	MSc-Network Technology and Management
10	Brainware University, WB	MSc-Hardware & Networking
No. of Total Universities 10		Total PG Programs 16

The universities offered by the programs in networking and allied fields are available in two platform in first, programs are offered directly without any kind of concentration viz.—

- MSc (Tech)- IT Infrastructure Management Services
- MSc (Tech)- Mobile Application
- MSc-IT (Cyber Security)

Whereas, many universities are offered the Networking as a concentration within the broader branch viz. –

- MSc-IT (Network Administration), Navrachana University, Gujarat
- MSc-IT- Mobile Computing, GLS University, Gujarat
- MSc-IT- Network & System Administration, GLS University, Gujarat etc.

It is worthy to note that universities of other categories are also engaged in offering different newer programs and skill based areas and among these Deemed Universities are important. And State Universities and Central Universities may also start related program with good numbers in future.

Concluding Remarks with Suggestions

This paper is a kind of review of existing work and also new study in the area of Computer and Information Sciences to learn about the new age program in Networking Technologies. It is important to note that at Bachelors level most of the universities have not started specialization on the area, and thus at Bachelors level this may be started either as a full fledged degree or as concentration. Additionally as Computer Application is a broader and

most commonly available program in India so the program may be started with following nomenclature—

- BSc-IT (Networking Technology)
- BSc-CS (Networking Technology)
- BSc-CA (Networking Technology)
- BCA (Networking Technology)

The program may also offered with other nomenclatures and emerging areas and at Masters level also these emerging specialization may be offered. India is a developing nation and thus modernization of higher education is highly required.

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